

ISic3367

I.Sicily inscription 3367

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

oracle

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011-04 and 2013-10-02 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Found by a local farmer in the area of Colle Orbo c.1968

Coordinates

37.054649, 14.899828

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 66528

Physical Description

Upper left part of a rectangular stele, broken across the middle in two (joining) pieces. The stele is cleanly cut on the right, finished and intact on the left side and on top, broken off below; the rear is roughly worked and uneven. The upper part of the stele is marked off by a moulding, which extends around the left side also (but not the rear). Above the moulding on the front is relief decoration in the form of (the left side of) a winged altar; above this the front face is missing to a depth of several centimetres. The upper fragment (A) is max H. 32.3, W 8 cm, D 16.6cm at top and 18.1 cm at bottom; the lower fragment (B) is max H 31.4 cm, W 8 cm, D 16.8 cm (top) to 18.2 cm (bottom).

Dimensions

Height 63 cm

Width 8 cm

Depth 16.6-18.2 cm

Layout

The text is neatly laid out with a clear left margin on a single field below the moulding.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters are regular and deeply cut, with slightly pronounced serifs at the end of strokes. Alpha is broad with straight bar, and occasional tendency to apex at the top; beta has equal sized, closed, shallow loops; epsilon has shorter middle bar and slightly outward pointing top and bottom bars; zeta is formed by a vertical with horizontals top and bottom; theta is slightly ovoid in form, with a complete cross bar; kappa has short, equal length tails; Mu has slightly inward leaning first and final strokes, with the middle strokes meeting well above the middle of the line; nu has a shorter right hand stroke, with the lower angle above the line; omicron is small and mid-line; Pi has a slightly shorter right hand vertical; rho has small closed eye, of varying form (rounded or elongated); sigma has slightly outward facing top and bottom strokes and the middle strokes are sometimes rounded at the join; upsilon has shallow spreading upper strokes; phi has a rounded eye, with extended vertical stroke; chi is consistently slightly larger than other characters; omega open, slightly smaller and above the line, with horizontal tails. A horizontal stroke is visible above and

the left of the first letter of lines 6 and 26.

Letter heights:

Line 1-39: 5-6 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. τῶι Διὸς ἀγαθῶι Δ[---]
2. ρημένους χρη[---]
3. τᾶμ παίδων Μ[---]
4. γραφὰν καὶ τ[---]
5. τάσδε τὰς ἱερὰς[---]
6. αὐδάσω τάδε [---]
7. θεῖα μέγ γάρ [---]
8. θνειτὰ καταβ[---]
9. πλαζόμενομ[---]
10. ἄλλοτε δὲ φθ[---]
11. ἔσται δ'άμαρ ο[---]
12. τῶι φῶς ἐκβλα[---]
13. ἐκ κόλπων Ἰ[---]
14. πολλ[---]
15. [ἦμο]ς ἐν Ψ[---]
16. [έ]ν τοῖς φυ[---]
17. [ρ]θωσ[---]
18. [π]άνο[---]
19. δέξει Δ[---]
20. δαίμω[ν---]
21. αἴσια τοιο[---]
22. τοὺς δ' ἀχαρί[στους---]
23. ὑὸς δὲ ὑῶν [---]
24. λαοῖς λαπε[---]
25. πλουτοφόρο[ς---]
26. οὔτος ὁ χρησ[μὸς---]
27. στά φανείς [---]
28. ἐμ Παμφυ[λία][---]
29. ἱεροῦ Εὐκλος [---]
30. δὲ ἐγ Κρήτα[ι---]
31. καὶ ἄλλους [---]
32. παρ' ἄρνὸν Ἰ[---]
33. λιμὸν ἔστ[---]

- 34. γαδδαίων [---]
- 35. νϋγ γραφὰμ[---]
- 36. καὶ διακοσί[---]
- 37. πρεσβυτέρ[---]
- 38. θεσιν [τῶ]γ Γ[---]
- 39. ἐπὶ μα[---]
- 39a. [---]

Apparatus

Preliminary text based upon autopsy and photograph, with reference to editions of Manganaro and Gallavotti

Manganaro 1981: ἦμ ς ἐν ψ[- (it appears Manganaro could read the first part of the line, but nothing is now visible).

Manganaro 1981: χρησμ[ὸς], but there is no trace after the sigma

Manganaro 1981: φανείσ [, but there is no trace after the sigma

Manganaro 1981: Παμφυλ[ία], but there is no trace after the upsilon

Manganaro 1981: γα(ν) δαιων [-, but the stone is clear, as Gallavotti 1983

Translation

Commentary

The stone was first published by Manganaro 1981 in association with ISic2754 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic2754>] , the two seemingly having been discovered together, or at least in close proximity; the letter forms are essentially identical, and the texts were probably cut by the same hand.

Manganaro 1981 and Parke 1986 noted the further potential relevance of ISic1040 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1040>] .

Digital identifiers:

TM 645596

EDCS 71000507

PHI 333746

PHI 331330

PHI 331387

PHI 332318

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3367. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358455>

ΤΑΙΣ ΚΑΤΑ ΤΟ
ΚΑΤΑ ΤΟ
ΤΑΙΣ ΠΑΙΔΕΥΣΙ
ΤΑΙΣ ΑΡΧΑΙΟΤ
ΤΑΙΣ ΔΕ ΤΑΙΣ
ΑΥΤΑΙΣ ΤΟΙΣ
ΒΕΙΑΜΕΓ ΓΑΡ
ΘΜΕΙΤΑ ΚΑΤΑ
ΠΛΑΤΟΝΟΜΟΣ
ΑΛΛΟΤΕΣ ΔΕ ΦΘ
ΕΣΤΑΙ ΔΑΜΑΡΟ
ΤΩΙ ΦΛΕΚΕΛΑ
ΕΚΚΟΛΠΟΝΟ
ΤΟΛ

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ΙΕΡΟΥΘΕΟΚΛΑ
ΔΕ ΕΓΚΡΗΤΕ
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ΠΑΡΑΡΝΟΝ
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ΓΑΔ ΔΑΙΩΝ
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ΚΑΙ ΔΙΑΚΟΕ
ΠΡΕΣΒΥΤΕ
ΘΕΣ ΜΟΝΕΙ
ΠΙΜ

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del
06/05/2014